

ENGAGED BUDDHISM AND THE BODHISATTVA IDEAL IN VIETNAM

Ven. Le Huu Nguyen Vu

Research Scholar, Mahaprajapati Gautami Subharti School of Buddhist Studies

Ras Bihari Bose Subharti University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India

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Introduction

The Bodhisattva ideal is the cornerstone of Mahāyāna Buddhism, which representing the highest aspiration of a practitioner who seeks not only personal liberation but also the liberation of all sentient beings. This Bodhisattva aspect has inspired countless Buddhists across Asia based on compassion, wisdom, and fulfill the perfections. In Vietnam, a country with a rich Buddhist heritage for long period, shaped by both indigenous traditions and Chinese Mahāyāna Buddhism influences, with the Bodhisattva ideal has found particularly vibrant expression. Vietnamese devotion to *Avalokiteśvara* (*Quan Âm*), the emphasis on compassion in Buddhist practice, and the social engagement of modern Buddhist leaders testify to the vitality of this ideal.

During the twentieth century, Vietnam faced decades of political instability, war, and social upheaval. In such a context, Buddhism could not remain confined to temples and meditation halls. This gave promote to the Engaged Buddhism (Phật giáo Dẫn thân), a movement that reinterpreted the Bodhisattva path in terms of directly deal with social service, humanitarian work, and peace activism. The most famous and a prominent monk, writer, and peace activist, Venerable Thích Nhất Hạnh, became the leading person of Engaged Buddhism in Vietnam and later worldwide. His idea was that a real Bodhisattva in today's world should help people by dealing with all kinds of suffering, from war and environmental ruin to poverty and being forced to move.

This article examines the Bodhisattva ideal within Vietnamese Buddhism, its historical evolution, and its reformation through Engaged Buddhism. To state that Engaged

Buddhism in Vietnam exemplifies a dynamic manifestation of the Bodhisattva path, harmonizing inward development with external service, and that it imparts significant insights for world society in the twenty-first century.

The Bodhisattva Ideal in Mahāyāna Buddhism

The main concept of the Bodhisattva ideal is based on Mahāyāna Buddhist philosophy and practices of perfections. Unlike from the Theravada method of the Arahant, who seeks liberation for oneself, however, for the Bodhisattva vows to remain in the cycle of birth and death until all beings attain liberation. This ideal is based on the Bodhisattva vows, which focus on universal compassion and selfless dedication.

The Six Pāramitās

For the Bodhisattva path, according to the Mahayana Buddhism, is traditionally outlined by the Six Pāramitās (perfections):

1. Dāna (Generosity): Giving material help, protection, and the gift of the Dhamma.
2. Śīla (Morality): Living ethically and maintain the moral conduct by the Five Precepts and social responsibility.
3. Kṣānti (Patience): Cultivating tolerance, forgiveness, and endurance.
4. Vīrya (Effort): Perseverance in wholesome deeds for self and others.
5. Dhyana (Meditation): Meditation means for developing concentration, awareness and mindfulness for stable and calm.
6. Prajñā (Wisdom): Prajna means understanding emptiness (śūnyatā), reality of the nature and interdependence. Actually, Buddhism in Vietnam, these perfections are not only the abstract ideals but also for the practical guidelines. Charity projects, moral discipline in community life, patience in times of conflict, perseverance in social work, mindfulness meditation, and the wisdom of interbeing all reflect the Bodhisattva path.

Avalokiteśvara (Quan Âm) in Vietnam

Among all Bodhisattvas, Avalokiteśvara (Quan Âm) have a special place in Vietnamese Buddhism in present days. Respect as the symbolize of compassion, Quan Âm is several depicted paintings can see in temples, shrines, and folk art. Devotees call upon her in times of crisis, dangers, illness, or hardship. The widespread devotion to Quan Âm shows how deeply compassion permeates Vietnamese religious culture. This type of devotion also provided fertile ground for the rise of Engaged Buddhism: The Bodhisattva of Compassion was no longer only an object of veneration but also a model for social engagement.

Historical Context of Engaged Buddhism in Vietnam

According to history, Vietnamese Buddhism combined with Mahāyāna teachings, Zen practice (especially the Trúc Lâm tradition), and indigenous cultural elements. However, during the 20th century Vietnamese Buddhists confronted with unprecedented challenges and difficulties, that means French colonialism, Japanese occupation, civil conflict, and the Vietnam War created widespread suffering. During these crises, many Buddhists felt the need to translate spiritual ideals into social action.

Thích Nhất Hạnh and the Rise of Engaged Buddhism

The Most Venerable Thích Nhất Hạnh (1926–2022) was a central figure in this transformation of engaged Buddhism. He guided that educated in both traditional Buddhist monasticism and Western scholarship, he recognized that Buddhism had to respond to the suffering of ordinary people. Around 1960s, the most Venerable coined the term “Engaged Buddhism”, which meant applying Buddhist principles to issues such as war, poverty, education, and health care.

In 1964, he founded the School of Youth for Social Service (SYSS) in Vietnam. This organization trained young Buddhists to rebuild bombed villages, establish schools, run medical clinics, and organize agricultural cooperatives and because of these efforts embodied the Bodhisattva spirit of compassion in action because of his guidelines, many volunteers risked their lives and some were killed while serving war-torn communities, demonstrating a profound commitment to the Bodhisattva vows.

Social and Political Struggles in Vietnam

The Buddhist community in Vietnam also played a role in protests against injustice and violence because during the Vietnam War, Buddhists organized participated non-violent demonstrations for peace and religious freedom. The self-immolation of Thích Quảng Đức in 1963, though tragic, was a dramatic expression of compassion and moral resistance, reflecting the Bodhisattva willingness to sacrifice for others.

The Bodhisattva Ideal in Engaged Buddhist Practice

The method of Engaged Buddhism reinterprets the Bodhisattva path as an active response to social realities and several themes illustrate this connection: as teaching in compassion for all, do not create the harmful things to others and so on. During the Vietnam War, they pushed for communication and reconciliation. They didn't support any political group, and the Bodhisattva ideal let them see past national boundaries and recognize that everyone is human. The Most Venerable Thích Nhất Hạnh was forced to leave Vietnam in

1966. He brought Engaged Buddhism to other countries and started the Plum Village community in France. His books and teachings have moved over the world, influencing those who work for peace, the environment, and mindfulness. In this way, the Bodhisattva ideal went across national borders and became a worldwide movement.

The Contemporary Relevance of the Bodhisattva Ideal in Vietnam

Today in Vietnamese Buddhism, the practice of Bodhisattva ideal is rapidly modernizing, with challenges such as urbanization, consumerism, social inequality, and environmental issues. Engaged Buddhism continues to provide inspiration:

(i) Charity and Social Welfare Work: Many Vietnamese temples, even nuns and Buddhist Organizations organize free medical camps, sharing food, and provide disaster relief for victims during floods and typhoons and other disasters.

(ii) Education and Social Welfare: Monasteries and Buddhist NGOs organizations established free schools and scholarship programs for needy children.

(iii) Youth Engagement: Vietnamese young Buddhists are studying to the teachings of mindfulness, empathy and inter-being, applying them for personal growth, family welfare and social well-beings.

(iv) Environmental Protection: Inspired by The Most Venerable Thích Nhất Hạnh's call for ecological responsibility, to Buddhist groups promote tree planting, clean-water initiatives, maintaining environment and sustainable lifestyles.

The Bodhisattva ideal ensures that Buddhist practice in Vietnam is not only about maintain morality, chanting and meditation but also about compassionate action in society.

Conclusion

The Bodhisattva ideal has been a guiding light for Vietnamese Buddhism for centuries, embodying compassion, wisdom, and altruism. In the modern era, this ideal took a new form through Engaged Buddhism, which demonstrated that spiritual practice must include social service, humanitarian action, and peace-building. The vision of the most Venerable Thích Nhất Hạnh and his followers proved that the Bodhisattva is not merely a mythical figure but also a living example of mindful action and compassion in society. Nowadays, in our world have facing crises of war, inequality, and environmental degradation, the Vietnamese model of Engaged Buddhism offers profound lessons. The practice and the way of Engaged Buddhism reminds us that the true measure of spirituality is not escape from the world but compassionate engagement with it moreover, by walking and following the

Bodhisattva path, Vietnamese Buddhists have contributed not only to their nation but also to the global movement for peace and harmony.

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